

humantech

D3.3 – Hyperspectral material scanning approach

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D3.3 – Hyperspectral material scanning approach

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
HIS	Hyperspectral imaging
NIR	Near-Infrared
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
GUI	Graphical user interface
PCA	Principal component analysis

Abstract

This report encapsulates an exploration of hyperspectral imaging technologies for material identification processes in construction settings. The initial focus on sensor selection involved an in-depth investigation of the MicaSense RedEdge multispectral sensor. Unforeseen challenges led to a strategic shift, leveraging the available FX10 hyperspectral camera by Specim. The subsequent data acquisition phase covered the acquisition setup, software utilization, and the systematic creation of a dataset featuring diverse construction materials. Data analysis encompassed detailed preprocessing steps, including calibration and specific bands selection to replicate the data that would have been acquired with the initially considered RedEdge multispectral sensor. A Principal Component Analysis unveiled underlying patterns within the dataset, highlighting distinctive spectral signatures of different construction materials.

The HumanTech project

The European construction industry faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its productivity, and become greener, making efficient use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that

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can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding, and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

- **Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence** that allow them to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site in which they are.
- **Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment.** From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance for them to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.
- An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs) of construction sites** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modelling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers, and autonomous machines.

The **HumanTech consortium** is formed by 22 organisations — leading research institutes and universities, innovative hi-tech SMEs, and large enterprises, construction groups and a construction SME representative — from 10 countries, bringing expertise in 11 different disciplines. The consortium is led by the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence's Augmented Vision department.

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1. Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of modern construction sites, ensuring the safety of workers, effective management of resources, and promoting sustainable practices have become paramount concerns. Central to addressing these aspects is the identification of construction materials, a critical factor influencing various facets of construction processes. In fact, this identification not only plays a crucial role in the early detection of hazardous substances but also facilitates targeted material recovery and reuse, thereby minimizing waste and fostering a circular economy.

Traditional methods of material identification in construction sites typically rely on visual inspection or manual sampling, often leading to inaccuracies and time-consuming processes. These methods may fail to detect hazardous materials or differentiate between similar-looking materials, potentially endangering workers' health and safety. Moreover, manual sampling can be labor-intensive and may not provide sufficient information to accurately assess material composition and suitability for reuse or recycling.

The HumanTech project proposes an innovative approach that integrates hyperspectral imaging systems into Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs). This would represent a paradigm shift in how to perceive and interact with construction materials. By capturing a wider range of wavelengths than traditional cameras, hyperspectral imaging can distinguish materials based on their spectral signatures, which are unique patterns of electromagnetic radiation associated with specific materials. This capability enables accurate material classification and detection of hazardous substances even when concealed by layers of materials or covered with debris.

The integration of hyperspectral imaging for in-depth material recognition could offer several benefits for construction sites:

1. **Enhanced Safety:** accurate identification of hazardous materials can prevent accidents and protect workers from exposure to harmful substances.
2. **Efficient Resource Management:** accurate material classification facilitates resource recovery and reuse, reducing waste and contributing to a circular economy.
3. **Automated Quality Control:** automated material inspection can identify defects and inconsistencies in construction materials, ensuring structural integrity and quality standards.

4. **Reduced Environmental Impact:** efficient material recovery and reuse minimize the need for virgin resource extraction, contributing to a more sustainable construction industry.

The objective of Task 3.3 of the HumanTech project, originally led by Naska.AI, was indeed the integration of hyperspectral sensing into the UGV platform provided by Naska.AI, in order to recover in-depth material information. The main activities of the task included the selection of an appropriate hyperspectral sensor for material scanning, the development of architecture diagrams for sensor integration, the creation of drivers for sensor fusion, and the implementation of a detection software module for hyperspectral material scanning.

However, with Naska.AI's withdrawal from the HumanTech project in August 2023, the task leadership shifted to STAM, and the objective of the task had to be reassessed.

STAM inherited the work already conducted by Naska.AI, which included a thorough market search for hyperspectral cameras to identify the most suitable sensor meeting HumanTech's requirements. Unfortunately, the purchase of the sensor selected by Naska.AI proved unfeasible due to time constraints. Consequently, a pragmatic decision was made to utilize an available hyperspectral camera in STAM laboratory, ensuring promptly progress in acquiring and analyzing data.

The revised objectives of the task subsequently focused on:

- In a laboratory environment, acquiring new samples of materials closely resembling those that could be acquired by the sensor initially selected by Naska.AI.
- Manually analyzing the acquired samples to demonstrate the feasibility of discriminating between different construction materials, with a specific emphasis on showcasing this capability for a set of three distinct materials.

In summary, the primary aim of Task 3.3 remained focused on demonstrating that hyperspectral imaging is an effective method to differentiate between various construction materials in a real-world context, despite the adjustments made in response to Naska.AI's withdrawal.

The present document provides a detailed description of the work conducted by both Naska.AI and STAM to achieve these objectives.

2. Hyperspectral imaging

Hyperspectral imaging is an advanced sensing technology that transcends the limitations of traditional imaging systems by capturing a vast array of spectral information across a broad range of wavelengths. Unlike conventional RGB cameras that record three visible bands of color (red, green, and blue), hyperspectral imaging systems acquire data across numerous contiguous spectral bands, often spanning the ultraviolet, visible, and infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum (Figure 1). Each pixel in a hyperspectral image corresponds to a unique spectrum, providing a detailed fingerprint of the materials present in the scene.

Figure 1: RGB vs Hyperspectral imaging¹

The key to hyperspectral imaging lies in its ability to discern subtle differences in the spectral signatures of materials. Every material reflects, emits, or absorbs light in a distinct manner, resulting in a characteristic spectral profile. By analyzing these unique signatures, hyperspectral imaging enables the identification and differentiation of materials based on their specific chemical composition, surface properties, or structural characteristics.

Hyperspectral imaging involves using an imaging spectrometer, also known as a hyperspectral camera, to collect spectral information. The device measures thousands or hundreds of thousands of spectra to create a hyperspectral data cube comprising position, and wavelength information. Figure 2 shows the concept of the hypercube data captured by a spectral imaging system. The spectral imaging data can be visualized as

¹ <https://www.specim.com/technology/what-is-hyperspectral-imaging/>

a three-dimensional (3-D) cube or a stack of multiple two-dimensional (2-D) images because of its intrinsic structure, in which the cube face is a function of the spatial coordinates, and the depth is a function of wavelength.

Figure 2: Hyperspectral data cube ²

The key components and concepts related to hyperspectral data cubes are:

- **Spatial Dimensions:** the first two dimensions of the data cube correspond to the spatial dimensions of the scene. Each pixel in the hyperspectral data cube represents a specific location in the scene, and these pixels are organized in rows and columns.
- **Spectral Dimension:** the third dimension of the data cube corresponds to the spectral dimension. It represents different wavelengths or bands of electromagnetic radiation. Each layer in the spectral dimension corresponds to a specific wavelength or band. The range of wavelengths captured depends on the sensor used.
- **Data Values:** at each spatial location (pixel) and for each wavelength, the data cube contains a value that represents the radiance or reflectance of the surface at that specific combination of spatial coordinates and wavelength. Radiance is a measure of the electromagnetic energy emitted or reflected by the surface, while reflectance is the ratio of reflected to incident light.

² <https://it.mathworks.com/help/images/getting-started-with-hyperspectral-image-analysis.html>

The hyperspectral cube, which defines each hyperspectral image, can be built according to different acquisition modalities, depending on the type of hyperspectral sensor used. Some key approaches are illustrated in Figure 3 and are:

- a) **Whiskbroom:** the scene is scanned point by point, capturing one spectral band at a time, i.e. a column within the image cube. A relative movement between the scene and the camera is required, to scan the scene along two dimensions.
- b) **Pushbroom:** similar to whiskbroom, but instead of a single point, a line of adjacent spatial positions is simultaneously acquired. In this case the relative movement between the scene and the camera is along just one dimension.
- c) **Staring:** involves keeping the image field of view fixed and obtaining images one wavelength after another.
- d) **Snapshot:** this method captures the entire hyperspectral cube in a single snapshot, providing instantaneous spectral information for all pixels. However, it often involves complex optics and computational methods.

Figure 3: Different techniques used for building a hyperspectral cube: (a) whiskbroom, (b) pushbroom, (c) staring, and (d) snapshot³

3. Sensor selection

In the pursuit of conducting a comprehensive and efficient hyperspectral analysis for the identification of construction materials, careful consideration was given to the selection of the spectral sensor. The chosen sensor needed to meet specific criteria to ensure its suitability for the specific scenario considered in the HumanTech project.

³ Kuswidiyanto, Lukas Wiku, Hyun-Ho Noh, and Xiongzhe Han. "Plant Disease Diagnosis Using Deep Learning Based on Aerial Hyperspectral Images: A Review." *Remote Sensing* 14.23 (2022): 6031.

One primary consideration was the physical dimension of the spectral sensor, as it was intended to be mounted on a UGV. The requirement for compactness was crucial to enhance mobility and flexibility during data acquisition. In addition, for the same reason, the sensor had to be lightweight.

To optimize the data acquisition process and streamline the deployment of the sensor in dynamic environments, a snapshot sensor was deemed essential (Figure 3). Unlike traditional scanning sensors that require movement to capture a scene, a snapshot sensor allows for the acquisition of an entire hyperspectral cube in a single shot. This characteristic minimizes the need for intricate movement setups, enhancing efficiency and adaptability in various scenarios.

Another key aspect to consider was the coverage of relevant wavelengths for the effective identification of materials commonly found in construction environment, such as brick, concrete, stone, and wood.

3.1. Preliminary NIR acquisitions

STAM has a deep background experience with hyperspectral sensors, mainly used for robotic sorting systems. For this reason, in its laboratory, STAM has some hyperspectral cameras available, which could be used to provide some preliminary data to facilitate the selection of the optimal spectral sensor for the HumanTech project.

In particular, for these preliminary experiments, the RedEye sensor by Inno-Spec was chosen. It is a high-performance pushbroom hyperspectral imaging camera that operates in the near-infrared (NIR) range from 950 to 1700 nm. Its datasheet is reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Inno-Spec – RedEye Datasheet

Spectral range	950-1700 nm
Pixel resolution	3.2 nm/pixel
Spectral bands	256
Spatial samples	320
Maximum frame rate	330 fps
Dimensions (L x W x H)	400 x 184 x 180 mm

Weight	7 kg
Power input	12 V DC (+-10%)

Given STAM's typical industrial applications of such sensors, the acquisition setup followed an industrial orientation (Figure 4). The camera, being of the pushbroom type (Figure 3), requires relative motion between itself and the scene. Consequently, it is mounted on a conveyor belt, upon which the samples designated for analysis are carefully positioned. To optimize spectral differentiation within the near-infrared (NIR) range, a specialized lighting system, based both on halogen and LED technology, illuminates the samples.

Figure 4: NIR acquisition set-up at STAM laboratory

The sensor was employed to capture samples of three distinct materials: brick, concrete, and stone. Small pieces of these materials were positioned on the conveyor belt, and NIR hyperspectral cubes were acquired (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Image of a brick sample extracted from a NIR hyperspectral cube

The spectral information of some pixels for each material were then extracted from the hyperspectral cubes, to analyse their spectral plot.

Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 report the spectral plots of pixels corresponding to brick, concrete, and wood, respectively. These graphs display the wavelength (X-axis) acquired by the sensor, totalling 256 wavelengths, against the intensity values (Y-axis) acquired for each specific wavelength.

Figure 6: Spectral plot in the NIR range of brick pixels

Figure 7: Spectral plot in the NIR range of concrete pixels

Figure 8: Spectral plot in the NIR range of stone pixels

Upon examining these graphs, it becomes apparent that pixels belonging to the same material share similar spectral signatures, while different materials showcase different signatures. In particular, the spectral graph of pixels from stone samples displays a signature entirely distinct from the other two materials, which, in contrast, exhibit a similar trend with varying intensity values. For instance, consider the peak observed around wavelength number 235 (approximately): in the case of brick, the peak registers an intensity value of over 5000, whereas in the case of concrete, it hovers around 3500.

This experiment represented only a preliminary study to provide some tangible examples of what could be done with hyperspectral images and showcasing initial results within the near-infrared (NIR) spectral range.

3.2. Multispectral sensor selection

Different studies in the literature investigate the analysis of construction materials using different types of sensors. Two publications by Zohreh Zahiri were considered particularly interesting in the context of this experiment.

One first paper⁴ explores the use of remote sensing technologies, specifically multispectral imagery and LiDAR intensity data, to classify and characterize common building materials. The authors propose that these technologies can be used to efficiently and cost-effectively assess the material composition of buildings at a citywide scale. Some of the key findings of the study are:

- Multispectral imagery and LiDAR intensity data can be used to classify and characterize common building materials.
- Multispectral imagery alone can achieve high classification accuracy for concrete and mortar.
- Adding LiDAR intensity data provides a marginal improvement in accuracy for brick classification.
- Bricks of differing clays and firing temperatures were classified successfully.

The second paper⁵ compares the feasibility of using ground-based hyperspectral imaging and red-edge multispectral imaging for classifying building façade materials in situ. The results revealed that hyperspectral imaging surpassed multispectral imaging in terms of classification accuracy, achieving an average accuracy of 99% compared to 82.75% for multispectral imaging. This is likely due to the wider spectral range of hyperspectral imaging, which allows for a more detailed differentiation between materials.

⁴ Zahiri, Zohreh, Debra F. Laefer, and Aoife Gowen. "Characterizing building materials using multispectral imagery and LiDAR intensity data." *Journal of Building Engineering* 44 (2021): 102603.

⁵ Zahiri, Zohreh, et al. "A comparison of ground-based hyperspectral imaging and red-edge multispectral imaging for façade material classification." *Automation in Construction* 136 (2022): 104164.

In both studies, the multispectral sensor employed is the RedEdge camera by MicaSense⁶, whose datasheet is reported in Table 2. This sensor measures the light reflected in five different bands (red, green, blue, red edge, and near-infrared), providing high-resolution RGB and multispectral outputs.

Table 2: MicaSense – RedEdge Datasheet

Spectral bands	Blue: 475 nm
	Green: 560 nm
	Red: 668 nm
	Red Edge: 717 nm
	Near-IR: 842 nm
Sensor resolution	1456 x 1088
Capture rate	Up to three captures per second
Dimensions (L x W x H)	89 x 70 x 67 mm
Weight	3.5 kg
Power input	5.5/7.0/10W (standby, average, peak)

Based on the results of these two scientific publications, both hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and red-edge multispectral imaging can be used to classify and characterize common building materials. However, the RedEdge multispectral sensor offers several advantages over HSI for material classification on construction sites:

- Portability: the RedEdge sensor is more portable than most hyperspectral cameras, being lightweight and compact. This characteristic is particularly crucial for the HumanTech project, which involves mounting the sensor on a UGV.
- Accuracy: while HSI offers slightly higher classification accuracy than the RedEdge, the difference is often not significant for most construction site applications. For example, an accuracy of 82.75%, which is the average accuracy achieved with the RedEdge in the second study, is generally sufficient to identify the major types of materials found on construction sites.

⁶ <https://ageagle.com/drone-sensors/rededge-p-high-res-multispectral-camera/>

- Snapshot Capability: the RedEdge sensor operates in a snapshot mode, enabling the acquisition of an entire hyperspectral cube in a single shot.
- Affordability: the RedEdge sensor is significantly more cost-effective than HSI cameras, due to its smaller number of spectral bands and simpler sensor design.

In conclusion, the RedEdge multispectral camera by MicaSense stands out as a cost-effective, portable, and efficient solution for material classification on construction sites. Its ability to identify common materials with sufficient accuracy makes it a versatile tool for a variety of construction site applications. Hence, for the HumanTech project, the RedEdge multispectral camera emerged as the optimal choice, aligning with the specific requirements and objectives of the experiment.

3.3. Sensor availability

Regrettably, as mentioned in the introductory section of this document, the purchase of the RedEdge multispectral sensor was not feasible.

To address this challenge and ensure the ongoing progress of the task, the decision was made to explore the hyperspectral sensors currently available in the STAM laboratory. The goal was to determine if any of these sensors could capture data resembling what would have been acquired by the RedEdge camera.

For example, the RedEye hyperspectral sensor by InnoSpec used for the preliminary study presented in Section 3.1, was not suitable to substitute the RedEdge. This is because the spectral range of the RedEye (900-1700 nm) is not compatible with the wavelengths considered by the RedEdge (475, 560, 668, 717, and 842 nm).

Fortunately, a hyperspectral sensor covering all five wavelengths of the RedEdge was finally available. Specifically, the FX10 camera by Specim, a high-performance line-scan hyperspectral camera operating in the visible and near-infrared (VNIR) region, capturing data from 400 to 1000 nm. Its datasheet is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Specim – FX10 Datasheet

Spectral range	400-1000 nm
Spectral resolution (FWHM)	5.5 nm (mean)
Spectral sampling/pixel	2.7 nm

Spectral bands	448
Spatial samples	512
Maximum frame rate	327 FPS full range
Dimensions (L x W x H)	150 x 85 x 71 mm
Weight	1.3 kg
Power input	12 V DC (+-10%)

Given the circumstances, utilizing the FX10 camera was considered the best available option, and accordingly, the activities progressed acquiring data with this sensor.

4. Data acquisition

Once a suitable spectral sensor was selected, it was possible to proceed with the acquisition process of hyperspectral data cubes. This process was performed in the laboratory environment available at STAM premises.

4.1. Acquisition setup

The acquisition setup, illustrated in Figure 9, consists of three key components:

- The FX10 **hyperspectral camera** from Specim, whose datasheet is reported in Table 3.
- A dedicated **illumination system**, based on LED technology. As a matter of fact, the quality of illumination significantly influences the spectral contrast of imaged samples. Proper illumination enhances spectral differences, facilitating the differentiation and analysis of various features within the scene.
- Given that the camera operates on the pushbroom principle, necessitating relative motion between the camera and the scene to scan samples, a **conveyor belt** is employed. This component facilitates the required relative motion, moving the samples under the camera.

Figure 9: FX10 acquisition setup at STAM laboratory

4.2. Acquisition software

Specim provides a dedicated Graphical User Interface (GUI) designed to streamline the hyperspectral cube acquisition process from the FX10 sensor. The GUI provides a user-friendly platform for starting and stopping the acquisition process, as well as saving the acquired data. Users have the flexibility to manually adjust certain camera parameters, including exposure and the region of interest (ROI).

The GUI enables real-time visualization of the ongoing acquisition process, presenting a live stream of the visual data captured by the camera, creating an image line after line (Figure 10). Additionally, users can observe spatial data plots corresponding to a single line of acquisition at a specific wavelength (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Specim acquisition software – Application output stream of Wood sample

Figure 11: Specim acquisition software – Spatial data plot of Wood sample

Furthermore, the GUI facilitates the acquisition of dark and white references: a crucial step for the subsequent calibration of the system. This critical process is performed at the beginning of each session of acquisition, to ensure that the references accurately represent the current environmental conditions.

For each new acquisition, the GUI allows to save the following files:

- Raw data of the sample (.raw): containing the raw data of the hyperspectral cube.
- Header file of the sample (.hdr): this file contains metadata and information crucial for interpreting and processing the associated hyperspectral cube data, such as

the dimension of the cube (samples, bands, and lines), sensor information, and considered wavelengths.

- Image of the sample (.png): it represents an RGB image of the content of the hyperspectral cube.
- Dark reference (.raw and .hdr): containing the hyperspectral cube of the dark reference corresponding to the current acquisition session.
- White reference (.raw and .hdr): encompassing the hyperspectral cube of the white reference of the current acquisition session.

4.3. Dataset

Three different materials have been selected for this experiment: aluminium, concrete and wood. This selection was driven by the widespread use of these materials, underscoring their relevance in construction scenarios. Aluminium is often employed in structural components, concrete is a fundamental building material, and wood is prevalent in various structural and finishing elements.

Moreover, these materials exhibit diverse physical and chemical properties: aluminium possesses distinct metallic properties, concrete is known for its strength and durability, while wood is characterized by its natural and renewable qualities. This diversity enables the feasible identification of these materials through hyperspectral analysis based on their unique spectral signatures.

To ensure the realism of the acquired hyperspectral cubes and their practicality in a construction environment, the samples of materials collected for the experiment were meticulously selected. The samples had to satisfy specific criteria: they were flat, could fit on the conveyor belt (so they had a width equals to or less than 40 cm), and had a length exceeding 40 cm. These criteria were established with the intent to replicate hyperspectral cubes that realistically align with what could be acquired in a construction setting, where substantial samples such as wooden beams, concrete columns, and aluminium frames are commonly encountered. A picture representing some examples of samples collected is reported in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Examples of Aluminium, Concrete, and Wood samples

Under the setup described in Section 4 and using the Graphical User Interface presented in Section 4.2, hyperspectral cubes of these different samples have been acquired, resulting in a good number of data. Each pixel within a hyperspectral cube serves as an example of the material's spectrum represented in the cube. Typically, each cube comprises thousands of pixels, determined by the spatial dimensions of the camera (in the case of FX10, equal to 512) multiplied by the number of lines acquired.

The resulting dataset is detailed in Table 3, encapsulating the breadth of spectral information derived from the acquired hyperspectral cubes.

Table 4: Dataset composition

Material	Material label	N. of pixels
Aluminium	1	50300
Concrete	2	221028
Wood	3	189630

5. Data analysis and results

After the creation of a consistent dataset made of samples of three different construction materials, the next step consists in analysing the acquired data to demonstrate whether the considered materials present differences in the spectral range considered in this experiment, making possible their automatic identification.

5.1. Data preprocessing

Before proceeding with analysis, it is crucial to preprocess data. This step would initially include to check and correct any potential missing data in the dataset. Fortunately, as the data is created by a software, internal processes have already ensured its integrity, and the resultant dataset is devoid of any form of NaN or missing values.

The first necessary step consists in extracting the data from the raw hyperspectral cube and organize it into a structured table. This process facilitates efficient handling and manipulation of the data during subsequent steps.

Another relevant aspect of preprocessing is the calibration of data, a crucial step to ensure that the acquired data accurately reflects the true spectral characteristics of the scene.

Additionally, in this specific scenario, an indispensable preprocessing step involves the dimensionality reduction of the dataset, transitioning from a hyperspectral dataset to a multispectral one. This entails considering only a specific subset of bands extracted from the entire spectral range.

5.1.1. **Data cubes unpacking**

The unpacking process involves extracting data from the raw hyperspectral cube to transform it into a more accessible and analyzable table.

To accomplish this, Spectral Python (SPy)⁷, a pure Python module designed for processing hyperspectral image data, is employed. Since each cube is associated with a respective ENVI header file, it becomes possible to use the “spectral.io.envi” package of

⁷ <https://www.spectralpython.net/index.html>

SPy to open and load the content of the raw cube. The data can then be converted into a 3D NumPy⁸ array.

Following this step, a dataset table is created. Each row in this table corresponds to a distinct pixel representing the material, with the columns representing its spectral values across the 448 different wavelengths. An additional column is appended, denoting the material label, in accordance with the conversion outlined in Table 4.

Table 5 exemplifies a dataset representing Concrete samples, identified by the material label equal to 2.

Table 5: Example of dataset of Concrete samples (Label = 2) for the whole spectra acquisition

	1	2	3	4	...	181	182	183	184	...	445	446	447	448	Label
1	202	202	210	210	...	1439	1400	1350	1301	...	192	190	190	190	2
2	204	204	208	206	...	1516	1474	1410	1355	...	189	189	189	189	2
3	207	207	207	204	...	1578	1522	1479	1414	...	192	191	191	191	2
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
221026	210	210	204	216	...	1553	1487	1423	1376	...	192	189	189	189	2
221027	212	212	210	204	...	1635	1581	1520	1465	...	190	189	189	189	2
221028	206	206	210	212	...	1554	1499	1437	1372	...	190	187	187	187	2

5.1.2. Calibration

Accurate interpretation of hyperspectral data requires careful calibration to correct for variations in sensor response, illumination conditions, and other systematic errors. Without proper calibration, the data may contain artifacts, biases, and inconsistencies that can compromise the accuracy of subsequent analyses. Calibration is particularly important when aiming to quantify material properties or perform comparative analyses across different datasets.

The calibration process involves using dark and white references. The dark reference is an ideal absorber, absorbing all incident light across the entire spectrum. It captures the sensor's response in the absence of light, aiding in correcting internal sensor biases. The white reference is a perfect reflector, reflecting all incident light across the entire spectrum equally. It represents a perfectly reflective surface and is used to correct for

⁸ <https://numpy.org/>

variations in illumination conditions. Separate measurements of white and black references are acquired under the same illumination conditions as the sample data.

The calibration process consists in correcting each pixel value using the respective dark and white reference values, employing the Min-Max Scaling method described by the following equation:

$$CalibratedData = 255 * \frac{Data - DarkReference}{WhiteReference - DarkReference}$$

This formula not only calibrates the data but also normalizes it, scaling it to values between 0 and 255. This normalization ensures compatibility with standard image processing tools and libraries, where image pixels data typically ranges from 0 to 255. Additionally, it enhances the dataset's suitability for visualization purposes.

The outcome is a calibrated dataset (Table 6), organized into a table with the same structure as Table 5.

Table 6: Example of dataset of calibrated Concrete samples (Label = 2) for the whole spectra acquisition

	1	2	3	4	...	181	182	183	184	...	445	446	447	448	Label
1	32	32	41	38	...	82	79	76	73	...	4	4	4	4	2
2	38	38	32	34	...	87	84	80	77	...	4	4	4	4	2
3	36	36	28	27	...	91	88	85	80	...	5	3	3	3	2
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
221026	33	33	31	34	...	89	85	81	78	...	3	2	2	2	2
221027	32	32	34	29	...	95	91	87	84	...	3	4	4	4	2
221028	33	33	36	33	...	90	86	82	78	...	3	3	3	3	2

5.1.3. Bands selection

As the dataset originates from the FX10 hyperspectral camera by Specim, while the objective is to demonstrate the feasibility of material differentiation using the RedEdge-P multispectral camera from MicaSense, a meticulous data processing phase is essential to replicate, as accurately as possible, the data that would have been obtained by the latter sensor.

This critical step involves the selection of only five bands from the 448 hyperspectral bands acquired by the FX10, aligning them with the wavelengths considered by the RedEdge-P sensor. This process is facilitated by the header file generated by the software employed for hyperspectral data acquisition. Included in the file information is the

precise list of wavelengths considered by the sensor, as highlighted in yellow in the extract of a header file reported in Figure 13.

```
ENVI
description = {File imported into ENVI}
file type = ENVI
sensor type = fx10, cube-c1, Camera0S version: 1.1.3-64
acquisition date = DATE(yyyy-mm-dd): 2023-12-14
acquisition time = 2023-12-14T07:39:09.289Z
sensorid = 1210215
samples = 512
bands = 448
lines = 620
interleave = BIL
byte order = 0
header offset = 0
data type = 12
errors = {none}
fps = 114.99
tint = 8.45
binning = {1, 2}
default bands = {190, 116, 40}
himg = {1, 512}
hroi = {1, 512}
vimg = {1, 448}
vroi = {1, 448}
fodis = {0, 0}
fpa = 0.00
fpga = 40.98
board = 30.00
temp1 = 0.00
temp2 = 0.00
temp3 = 0.00
Wavelength = {
397.01,
398.32,
399.63,
400.93,
402.24,
403.55,
404.86,
406.17,
```

Figure 13: Extract of header file with complete list of wavelengths

In particular, the RedEdge-P sensor features spectral bands at wavelengths 475, 560, 668, 717, and 842 nm, as indicated in its datasheet (Table 2). Fortunately, the same exact values are included in the list of wavelengths of the FX10 sensor, respectively at the bands in positions 61, 125, 205, 241, and 332. This data is schematically represented in Table 7.

Table 7: Bands selection

	RedEdge-P	FX10	
	Wavelength [nm]	Wavelength [nm]	N. of band
Blue	475	475	61
Green	560	560	125
Red	668	668	205
Red-Edge	717	717	241
Near-IR	842	842	332

Following the selection of the five bands, the dataset undergoes dimensionality reduction. Specifically, from the original dataset with 448 bands columns, only columns 61, 125, 205, 241, and 332 are considered. This reduction results in a new version of the dataset, presented in Table 8, comprised of five bands columns and an additional column for the material label. Furthermore, the three tables corresponding to the three materials considered have been unified into a singular table containing all 460958 pixels considered in this experiment.

Table 8: Dataset of mixed samples after bands selection

	1	2	3	4	5	Label
1	38	27	36	59	128	1
2	40	29	36	58	109	1
3	40	28	36	56	104	1
---	...	...	...	...	...	...
59598	46	178	46	16	2	2
59599	49	188	48	17	3	2
59600	46	179	46	16	3	2
---	...	...	...	...	...	...
460956	70	236	74	28	7	3
460957	70	236	75	28	7	3
460958	71	237	74	28	7	3

5.2. Multispectral data plot

Once the dataset has been pre-processed, it is in its final version and the data it describes can be analysed.

In this step the spectral plot of the different materials is depicted on graphs. Figure 14 displays the plot of Aluminium pixels, Figure 15 presents the one for Concrete pixels, and Figure 16 showcases the plot for Wood pixels.

These graphs illustrate the intensity variations of the three materials under the five wavelengths considered. Within these visualizations, the marked line corresponds to the mean value across all pixels of that material, while the colored region spans the range between the mean minus the standard deviation and the mean plus the standard deviation.

Figure 14: Spectral plot of Aluminium pixels

Figure 15: Spectral plot of Concrete pixels

Figure 16: Spectral plot of Wood pixels

The same graphs are also reported all in one illustration in Figure 17, to facilitate comparison.

Figure 17: Spectral plot of Aluminium (blue), Concrete (purple), and Wood (orange) pixels

These plots are valuable for analyzing the spectral characteristics of the three considered materials. Different materials have unique spectral signatures, and by examining the spectral plot, it is possible to identify specific wavelengths at which a material exhibits distinctive features or absorption bands.

In particular, it is possible to notice that, for the considered wavelengths, the spectral plot of the Aluminium pixels differs significantly from the other two materials, possibly due to its metallic properties. Meanwhile, Concrete and Wood display similar plots but with different intensity values. Specifically, Wood demonstrates higher intensity values compared to Concrete. The resemblance in their plot could be due to similarities in their optical properties, surface characteristics, or composition in those particular regions of the spectrum.

5.3. [PCA analysis](#)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely utilized technique for analyzing extensive datasets containing a high number of dimensions/features per observation. Its purpose is to enhance data interpretability while retaining maximum information and facilitating the visualization of multidimensional data. Formally, PCA is a statistical method for reducing dataset dimensionality by linearly transforming the data into a new coordinate system, where (most of) the data variation can be described with fewer dimensions than the original data.

PCA is frequently used for analyzing hyperspectral data cubes using machine learning techniques. This is particularly valuable as hyperspectral data cubes, containing a large number of spectral bands, pose challenges such as computational complexity and overfitting, where the model performs well on the training data but poorly on new data. PCA addresses these issues by transforming high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional space, reducing computational complexity and improving the model's generalization performance.

The core mechanism of PCA involves identifying principal components (PCs), which are the most crucial directions of variation in the data. These components capture the largest variance and can reconstruct the original data with minimal information loss. By selecting a subset of principal components, data dimensionality can be reduced while retaining critical information. Principal components are linear combinations of original

variables, each capturing a different amount of variation. They are orthogonal to each other, meaning that they are uncorrelated.

In PCA, the scree plot is an important tool for understanding the variance in the data and selecting the number of components to retain for dimensionality reduction. It is a curve that displays how the explained variance changes as you consider an increasing number of principal components. The "elbow point" on the plot, where the curve levels off, is often chosen as the optimal number of components to retain, representing the majority of data variance. At this point, adding more principal components doesn't contribute significantly to explaining additional variance. The decision on the number of principal components to retain depends on analysis goals and the desired variance explanation. Insufficient components may result in information loss, while an excess may lead to overfitting.

5.3.1. PCA application

Using Principal Component Analysis to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset is typically beneficial when the original dataset has high dimensionality, and the goal is to capture the most important information while discarding less relevant details. In the case described in this document, the dataset considered is already a low-dimensional one (five dimensions), representing a multispectral cube rather than a hyperspectral one.

Nevertheless, performing PCA might still be useful for visualization purposes. In fact, reducing dimensions from five to a maximum of three enables 3D visualization, by projecting the data onto the three principal components. This can reveal cluster of patterns that were not immediately apparent in the original space.

Figure 18 illustrates the scree plot resulting from PCA application to the dataset, demonstrating that the first three principal components explain 99.7% (53.8% + 44.7% + 1.2%) of the data variance.

Figure 18: Scree plot of PCA analysis

The elbow point is usually located where the explained variance starts to show diminishing returns, and the curve becomes flatter. In the case visualized in Figure 18, PC3 contributes only 1.2% to the explained variance, and there is a substantial drop in the percentage from PC2 to PC3. Therefore, the elbow point is likely situated between PC2 and PC3. Based on the percentages obtained, it seems reasonable to retain the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2), as they collectively explain a substantial amount of variance (98.5%). This results in a reduction from a dimensionality of five to a more concise dimensionality of two. Retaining more components may not significantly contribute to explaining additional variance, considering the marginal contribution of PC3.

Having selected as principal components PC1 and PC2, a 2D representation of the data into this reduced space becomes feasible. Figure 19 provides a plot of the pixels contained in the dataset in this reduced 2D space, where pixels categorized under the Aluminium class appear as purple dots, Concrete pixels as green dots, and Wood pixels as yellow dots.

Figure 19: 2D representation of dataset into PC1-PC2 space

A discernible pattern emerges from this visualization, indicating that the pixels form three distinct clusters of points.

The presence of three distinct clusters in the 2D representation suggests a meaningful separation among the different classes within the dataset. This separation validates the significance of the methodology outlined in this document. Commencing with the selection of the multispectral camera, the careful choice of spectral bands, and the meticulous setup for data acquisition: each step in the process contributes to the creation of a meaningful dataset. The application of Principal Component Analysis further refines the data, ultimately leading to the creation of the 2D plot.

In essence, the creation of meaningful clusters in the 2D plot serves as a tangible outcome, verifying that the entire process - from initial camera selection to the application of PCA - has successfully achieved the goal of being able to differentiate the data based on their material composition. This validation reinforces the reliability and accuracy of the methodology, showcasing its applicability for subsequent steps, including the potential automation of material classification using machine learning algorithms.

In fact, the well-defined separation of clusters implies that the identified principal components capture the essential features that differentiate the materials. By

incorporating these components into a machine learning model, such as a classification algorithm, it becomes feasible to exploit the identified patterns for accurate and automated material classification. This approach not only simplifies the interpretation of complex datasets but also lays the foundation for practical applications, where the automated classification of materials can be invaluable for various industries, quality control processes, or scientific analyses.

6. Practical challenges and considerations

Before concluding the exploration of hyperspectral imaging in construction material identification, it is crucial to address practical challenges that may impact the method's real-world applicability. These considerations are vital for a comprehensive understanding of the technology's limitations and potential areas of improvement.

When transitioning from a controlled laboratory setting to a dynamic construction environment, several key considerations come to the forefront:

- In a real-world scenario, the camera should be mounted on a robotic arm or a mechanism to facilitate relative motion between the camera and the samples and replicate the functioning of the conveyor belt. Alternatively, the need for an elaborate mechanical setup can be avoided using a snapshot-type camera, such as the RedEdge from MicaSense.
- Unlike controlled laboratory environments, lighting conditions in real construction sites are less predictable. As already mentioned in this document, the quality of illumination significantly influences the spectral contrast of the imaged samples. For this reason, a proper illumination system is essential also in the real construction environment. This system should effectively illuminate the samples, compensating for natural lighting variations and minimizing the creation of shadows.
- Images acquired in a real-world scenario may capture multiple elements and materials simultaneously. For this reason, robust computer vision algorithms should be developed to segment the different elements present within the images. Subsequently, analyzing the spectra of a representative subset of pixels belonging to each segment facilitates precise material detection of each element.

An alternative strategy involves a comprehensive scan of all pixels in the image. By analyzing the spectral information of each pixel, it becomes possible to reconstruct the different elements captured by the materials detected. Additionally, exploring the integration of depth information, possibly through a combination of hyperspectral and depth sensors, can enhance the method's ability to spatially separate and classify multiple materials within a scene.

An additional critical consideration is the high variety of materials encountered in construction sites. To effectively train a hyperspectral imaging system for material identification, the quantity and diversity of training data must be extensive. The system needs exposure to a vast array of material spectra to recognize and differentiate between the diverse materials present in real-world scenarios. This necessitates the acquisition and annotation of a massive dataset covering a wide spectrum of construction materials, ensuring the robustness and reliability of the trained model in practical applications.

Moreover, it is essential to highlight that the diversity in training data extends beyond different materials. Variations within the same material category, such as different types of wood, are equally crucial. Including in the training set diverse samples of the same material but of distinct types enhances the model's ability to learn general features shared across various variants. This approach ensures that the model can generalize effectively, increasing the likelihood of accurately identifying unknown samples, even if they belong to different subtypes within a material category.

Effectively addressing these considerations ensures the adaptability of hyperspectral imaging techniques in real-world construction scenarios.

7. Conclusions

With the aim of advancing construction site material identification processes, this document reported a comprehensive exploration of hyperspectral imaging technologies.

Firstly, a meticulous consideration of sensor selection was performed, encompassing both preliminary acquisitions using the RedEye sensor by Inno-Spec and an in-depth investigation of the MicaSense RedEdge multispectral sensor. However, due to

unforeseen challenges in sensor purchasing, the focus shifted to the available FX10 hyperspectral camera by Specim.

The data acquisition phase thoroughly examined the FX10 sensor, covering the acquisition setup, software utilization, and the careful creation of a dataset featuring diverse construction materials. This phase laid the groundwork for the subsequent data analysis.

The data analysis phase comprised several key stages, commencing with detailed preprocessing steps. These steps included unpacking hyperspectral data cubes, conducting calibration processes, and selecting specific bands to replicate as closely as possible the data that would be acquired with the originally selected RedEdge multispectral sensor. Visual exploration of multispectral data plots provided valuable insights, laying the groundwork for a more sophisticated Principal Component Analysis (PCA) examination.

The PCA analysis served as a powerful tool in showing underlying patterns within the dataset. The results obtained through PCA highlighted the distinctive spectral signatures of different construction materials, validating the potential of hyperspectral imaging in this domain.

In conclusion, this report signifies a significant step toward leveraging hyperspectral imaging for construction material identification. Despite the challenges faced during the running of the task, the outcome of these activities is promising and underscore the potential of hyperspectral imaging technologies, paving the way for improved safety, resource management, and quality control within the dynamic realm of construction sites.